

Quinolinyl-azo-pyridine coordinated complexes of some 3d block metal ions: Synthesis, spectroscopic characterization and X-ray study

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5-(Pyridin-3-ylidiazanyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL) acts as anionic bidentate N,O-chelator to synthesize the complexes of composition $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]$ ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$) and $[M'L_2]$ ($M' = Ni^{II}$ and Zn^{II}). The complexes have been characterized by spectroscopic data. The molecular structure of $[MnL_2(H_2O)_2]$ has been confirmed by single crystal X-ray crystallography. Magnetic (bulk and EPR) properties of the complexes determine the electronic configuration. Redox properties of the complexes have been examined by cyclic voltammetric data.

Keywords: 5-(Pyridin-3-ylidiazanyl)quinolin-8-ol, 3d metal complexes, structure and spectra, EPR data, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

The design of multifunctional molecules of N-heterocycle and their metal complexes with desirable and predictable properties are of current interest¹⁻⁸. The metal complexes of the ligands having O, N and/or S donor centers have expanded enormously⁹⁻²⁵. In the development of coordination chemistry of N-donor centers - imine group, -N=C-, and the azo group, -N=N-, have taken active role. Considerable effort has now been given to functionalize 3-aminopyridine so that metal complexes may be synthesized that could display interesting properties. 3-Aminopyridine derivatives show bio-medical activity and one of the derivatives, 3-aminopyridine-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone is a ribonucleotide reductase inhibitor^{26,27}. This has encouraged us to synthesize 5-(pyridin-3-ylidiazanyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL), which reacts with $M(OAc)_2$ in methanol and acetonitrile mixture to synthesize $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]$ ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$) and $[M'L_2]$ ($M' = Ni^{II}$ and Zn^{II}) complexes. All these compounds are characterized by spectroscopic data. In case of $[MnL_2(H_2O)_2]$ the structure has been confirmed by single crystal X-ray crystallography. Magnetic and redox properties of the complexes are discussed.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

3-Aminopyridine, $M(OAc)_2$, $[Mn(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O]$, $[Co(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O]$, $[Ni(OAc)_2 \cdot 4H_2O]$, $[Cu(OAc)_2 \cdot H_2O]$, $[Zn(OAc)_2 \cdot 2H_2O]$ were purchased from Merck, India. Solvents were purified by standard procedure²⁸. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Microanalytical data (C, H and N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Spectroscopic data were obtained using the following instruments: UV-Vis spectra by Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model Lambda 25; FTIR spectra (KBr disk, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) by Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer model RX-1; the ¹H NMR spectra by Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer. Emission spectra were examined by LS 55 Perkin-Elmer spectrofluorometer at room temperature (298 K) in different solution under degassed condition. Using naphthalene as a reference with Φ_R , 0.21 in methanol²⁹ the fluorescence quantum yield of the complexes was determined. The emission spectra of the complexes were recorded upon excitation at same wavelength, maintaining nearly equal absorbance

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(-0.1) for the naphthalene and the complexes. The area of the emission spectra were integrated using the software available in the instrument and the quantum yield is calculated according to the following equation:

$$\Phi_S/\Phi_R = \left[\frac{A_S}{A_R} \right] \times \left[\frac{(Abs)_R}{(Abs)_S} \right] \times \left[\frac{\eta_S^2}{\eta_R^2} \right]$$

Here, Φ_S and Φ_R are the fluorescence quantum yield of the sample and reference, respectively. A_S and A_R are the area under the fluorescence spectra of the sample and the reference, respectively, $(Abs)_S$ and $(Abs)_R$ are the respective optical densities of the sample and the reference solution at the wavelength of excitation, and η_S and η_R are the values of refractive indices for the respective solvent used for the sample and reference. Fluorescence lifetimes were measured using a time-resolved spectrofluorimeter from IBH, UK. The instrument uses a picoseconds diode laser (NanoLed-03, 370 nm) as the excitation source and works on the principle of time-correlated single photon counting³⁰. The goodness of fit was evaluated by χ^2 criterion and visual inspection of the residuals of the fitted function to the data. Cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out using GC working micro-electrode, Pt-wire as auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl, Cl⁻ as reference electrode in dry DMF solution using [ⁿBu₄N][ClO₄] as supporting electrolyte under dry N₂ gas flushing. EPR spectra were recorded from 0 to 10000 Gauss at 298 K and 77 K with an X-band (9.15 GHz) Varian E-9 spectrometer. The magnetic susceptibility measurements of the powder crystalline sample of **1-4** were carried out at Sherwood Scientific Magnetic Susceptibility Balance model Mk1 at 300 K and the data were corrected using diamagnetic corrections from Pascal's Tables³¹. The estimation of Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn are performed by titrimetric (Mn and Cu), gravimetric (Ni) and complexometric (Co and Zn)³² assay, respectively.

Synthesis of 5-(pyridin-3-yl diazenyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL):

To ice-cold solution (0–5°C) of 3-aminopyridine (0.4 g, 4.2 mmol) in 2 N HCl sodium nitrite solution was added dropwise with continuous stirring. The diazotized solution was then added to the alkaline solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline with continuous stirring and acidity of the medium was maintained at pH 7. Deep red colour precipitate appeared, filtered and dried. It was then crystallized from hot methanol solution. Yield: 0.64 g, 61%. m.p. 190°C. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₀N₄O (%):

C, 67.19; H, 4.03; N, 22.39. Found (%): C, 67.10; H, 4.00; N, 22.50%; FT-IR (KBr, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1407; ν(C=N), 1620; ν(O-H), 3429; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃), δ(ppm), (J (Hz)): 7.24 (d, 2.58, 7-H), 7.46 (t, 3.21, 3-H), 7.64 (d, 8.53, 6-H), 8.12 (t, 8.48, 5'-H), 8.22 (d, 1.64, 4-H), 8.69 (d, 5.96, 4'-H), 8.89 (d, 5.78, 6'-H), 9.23 (d, 24.9, 2-H), 9.32 (s, 2'-H).

Preparation of the complexes:

5-(Pyridin-3-yl diazenyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL) (25.26 mg, 0.1 mmol) was dissolved in the mixture of methanol and acetonitrile (1:1, v/v) in hot condition and was added in drops to a methanol solution of Mn(OAc)₂·4H₂O (12.25 mg, 0.05 mmol) and dark red precipitate appeared. The precipitate was collected by filtration, washed with cold MeOH and dried over CaCl₂ *in vacuo*. The compound was dissolved in hot acetonitrile solution and allowed to cool slowly; red crystals were deposited on glass wall. It was filtered and dried *in vacuo*. The yield was 18.8 mg (64%). Microanalytical data of the complexes are as follows:

[MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (**1**) Anal. Calcd. for MnC₂₈H₂₂N₈O₄(%): C, 57.05; H, 3.76; N, 19.01; Mn, 9.33. Found (%): C, 57.10; H, 3.70; N, 19.11, Mn, 9.12; FT-IR (KBr disc, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1392; ν(C=N), 1569. [CoL₂(H₂O)₂] (**2**) Anal. Calcd. for CoC₂₈H₂₂N₈O₄(%): C, 56.67; H, 3.74; N, 18.88, Co, 9.93. Found (%): C, 56.60; H, 3.67; N, 18.78; Co, 9.48; FT-IR (KBr disc, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1396; ν(C=N), 1580. [NiL₂] (**3**) Anal. Calcd. for NiC₂₈H₁₈N₈O₂(%): C, 60.36; H, 3.26; N, 20.11; Ni, 10.53. Found (%): C, 60.65; H, 3.20; N, 19.82. Ni, 10.20; FT-IR (KBr disc, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1387; ν(C=N), 1572. [CuL₂(H₂O)₂] (**4**) Anal. Calcd. for CuC₂₈H₂₂N₈O₄(%): C, 56.23; H, 3.71; N, 18.74; Cu, 10.63. Found (%): C, 56.30; H, 3.68; N, 18.96; Cu, 10.40; FT-IR (KBr disc, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1400; ν(C=N), 1605. [ZnL₂] (**5**) Anal. Calcd. for ZnC₂₈H₁₈N₈O₂(%): C, 59.64; H, 3.22; N, 19.87; Zn, 11.60. Found (%): C, 59.55; H, 3.28; N, 19.80; Zn, 11.32; FT-IR (KBr disc, v, cm⁻¹): ν(N=N), 1385; ν(C=N), 1575; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃), δ(ppm), (J (Hz)): 9.45 (d, 10.20, 7-H), 7.54 (t, 4.30, 3-H), 6.88 (d, 9.25, 6-H), 7.80 (t, 4.04, 5'-H), 8.22 (d, 9.71, 4-H), 8.16 (d, 7.76, 4'-H), 8.56 (d, 7.33, 6'-H), 8.71 (d, 24.9, 2-H), 9.05 (s, 2'-H).

X-Ray crystallography of [MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (**1**):

The crystals of [MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (size: 0.15×0.11×0.08 mm³) were obtained by slow evaporation of the mixture of metha-

nol and acetonitrile solution. Crystallographic refinement data and selected geometric parameters are collected in Table 1. Data were collected by Bruker Smart Apex II CCD Area Detector. Fine-focus sealed tube was used as the radiation source of graphite-monochromatized Mo-K α radiation (λ , 0.71073 Å). Data were corrected for Lp and an empirical absorption correction. Data processing and empirical absorption correction were accomplished in the index range $-14 \leq h \leq 14$, $-6 \leq k \leq 6$, $-24 \leq l \leq 25$ using CRYSTAL CLEAR and ABSCOR³³ programs, respectively. The structure was solved by direct methods and followed by successive Fourier and difference Fourier syntheses. Full matrix least squares refinements on F2 were carried out using SHELXL-97^{34,35} with anisotropic displacement parameters for all non-hydrogen atoms. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to ride on the respective carbon atoms with isotropic displacement parameters equal to 1.2 times the equivalent isotropic displacement of their parent atom in all cases of aromatic units. Maximum and minimum transmissions are 0.957 and 0.930. Figures are drawn using ORTEP³⁶, PLATON³⁷ and MERCURY 2.2³⁸ softwares.

Table 1. Summarized crystallographic data of [MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (1)

[MnL ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂] (1)	
Formula	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₈ O ₄ Mn
Formula weight	589.48
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.15x0.11x0.08
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P 21/c
a (Å)	11.731(5)
b (Å)	5.316(5)
c (Å)	21.451(5)
β (°)	95.583(5)
V (Å) ³	1331.4(14)
Z	2
d _{calcd.} (g cm ⁻³)	1.470
F(000)	606.0
No. of collected reflections	17293
No. of independent reflections	2394
No. of reflections used	1599
No. of parameters	195
R ₁ ^a [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0576
WR ₂ ^b	0.1567
Goodness of fit	1.081
^a R = $\sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $, ^b WR ₂ = $[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, and w = $1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.0739P)^2 + 0.3024P]$ where P = $(F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$	

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation:

Diazotization of 3-aminopyridine followed by coupling with 8-hydroxyquinoline has synthesized a deep red coloured compound, 5-(pyridin-3-yl diazenyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL). The ¹H NMR spectrum in CDCl₃ of HL shows δ (OH) at 11.60 ppm and 3-pyridyl protons (2'-H to 6'-H) appear at 8.12 to 9.32 ppm and quinolinol protons (2-H to 7-H) appear at 7.24 to 8.22 ppm.

The reaction of HL with M(OAc)₂ in mixed solvent (methanol and acetonitrile, 1:1, v/v) has isolated dark red crystalline complex. Microanalytical and spectroscopic data support the compositions [ML₂(H₂O)₂] (M = Mn^{II} (1), Co^{II} (2) and Cu^{II} (4)) and [M'L₂] (M' = Ni^{II} (3) and Zn^{II} (5)). Molar conductance data show that the complexes are non-electrolyte in nature. The spectral, magnetic data and single crystal structure determination in one complex supports the composition. The ¹H NMR spectrum of [ZnL₂] shows that the aromatic protons are down field shifted by 0.3–2.2 ppm and severe perturbation is observed to quinolinolato 7-H which is shifted by 2.2 ppm. Besides, quinolinolato -OH is missing which supports the formation of Zn-O bond.

Infrared spectrum of HL shows moderately intense stretching at 1598 and 1374 cm⁻¹ those are due to ν (C=N) and ν (N=N), respectively alongwith a broad band centred at 3450 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to ν (OH). All the complexes show medium intense broad band(s) at 3400–3470 cm⁻¹ which is assigned to coordinated H₂O and moderately intense stretching at 1580–1590 and 1365–1375 cm⁻¹ those are due to ν (C=N) and ν (N=N), respectively.

The solution electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMF solution in 250–550 nm. All these complexes exhibit one/two intense band(s) at 250–400 nm range (Table 2). These transitions are presumably due to intra-ligand π - π^* and n- π^* transitions (Fig. 1). Red shifting of the band in the UV region by 50–100 nm from that of free ligand to the metal complexes support the coordination of ligand to metal ion. High intense transitions in visible region (460–500 nm) in some metal complexes are assigned to mixture of d-d and MLCT transitions. Some of the complexes again show weak d-d bands at >500 nm (Table 2).

Molecular structure of [MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (1):

A molecular view of [MnL₂(H₂O)₂] (1) is shown in Fig. 2

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of HL and $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{L})_2]$ (1); $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2); $[\text{NiL}_2]$ (3); $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (4); $[\text{ZnL}_2]$ (5) in DMF solution.

Table 2. UV-Vis and emission spectral data of HL and compounds

Compounds	λ_{max} (nm) ($10^{-3} \epsilon$ [$\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$])	λ_{ex} (nm)	λ_{em} (nm)
HL	268(4.6), 397(6.5), 513(2.2) ^b	243 ^a	346 ^a
$[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (1) ^b	267(21.32), 497(42.53)	267	409
$[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2) ^b	270(27.1), 480(48.48), 538 (0.87)	270	339
$[\text{NiL}_2]$ (3) ^b	266(45.09), 322(33.59), 389(26.78)	266	379
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (4) ^b	268 (19.75), 404 (18.31), 484 (27.47), 554 (0.75)	268	406
$[\text{ZnL}_2]$ (5) ^b	266(30.43), 347(6.86), 496(54.58)	347	414

^aSolvent: MeOH; ^bSolvent: DMF.

Fig. 2. Molecular structures of $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

and the selected bond parameters are listed in Table 3. The complex consists of a manganese atom surrounded by two N,O chelated ligands, L^- and two axial positions are occupied by two H_2O to constitute MnN_2O_4 coordination sphere. The chelate plane constituted by Mn(1), O(1), C(12), C(13), N(14) is almost planar (deviation < 0.002 Å). The pendant

Table 3. Selected bond lengths and bond angles of $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (1)

Bond lengths (Å)		Bond angles (°)	
Mn(1)-O(1)	2.183(3)	O(1a)-Mn(1)-O(1)	180.000(1)
Mn(1)-O(2)	2.238(3)	O(1)-Mn(1)-N(14)	102.75(10)
Mn(1)-N(14)	2.236(3)	O(1a)-Mn(1)-N(14)	77.25(10)
N(3)-C(2)	1.338(5)	N(14a)-Mn(1)-N(14)	180.000(2)
N(3)-C(4)	1.349(5)	O(2a)-Mn(1)-O(2)	180.000(1)
N(7)-N(8)	1.270(4)	O(1)-Mn(1)-O(2)	88.68(12)
N(14)-C(15)	1.329(5)	N(14)-Mn(1)-O(2)	89.50(12)
N(14)-C(13)	1.382(5)	C(2)-N(3)-C(4)	115.6(4)
C(12)-O(1)	1.292(4)	C(15)-N(14)-C(13)	119.6(3)
C(12)-C(13)	1.468(5)	C(13)-N(14)-Mn(1)	110.9(2)

pyridyl-N=N- makes dihedral of $8.60(17)^\circ$ with chelated Mn-quinolinolato plane. Two Mn-N(oxinato) [Mn-N(1), N(2)] and two Mn-O(phenolato) and two Mn-O(H_2O) bonds constitute the coordination zone where Mn(1) is seating at the centre of inversion. The chelate angle, Mn(N,O) is $77.25(10)^\circ$ and other angles about Mn^{II} conform to the octahedral bond angular data^{39,40}. The bond distances such as Mn(1)-N(14) (quinolinol-N), 2.236(3) Å; Mn(1)-O(1) (quinolinol-O), 2.183(3) Å and Mn(1)-O(2) (coordinated O of H_2O), 2.238(3) Å are comparable with literature data⁴¹.

The N=N distance is 1.270(4) Å which is closer to azo distance in 2-(*p*-tolylazo)imidazole ($d(\text{N}=\text{N})$, 1.257(6) Å)⁴². Intermolecular hydrogen bonds are observed between quinolinolato-O and coordinated H_2O of neighbouring molecule (O(2)-H---O(1): O(2)---O(1), 2.753(5) Å; O(1)---H, 1.92(3) Å; $\angle\text{O}(2)\text{-H}\text{---}\text{O}(1)$, $165(4)^\circ$; symmetry, 2-x, 1-y, 2-z) and forms 1-D chain. Pyridyl-N remains uncoordinated and is available to make contact through intermolecular bonding with neighboring molecule (O(2)-H---N(3): O(2)---N(3), 2.818(5) Å, N(3)---H, 2.04(4) Å; $\angle\text{O}(2)\text{-H}\text{---}\text{N}(3)$, $150(4)^\circ$; symmetry, 3-x, -y, 2-z) and forms 2D plane (Fig. 3). Presence of noncovalent $\pi\text{---}\pi$ interaction between pendant pyridyl ring (Cg(3)) and quinolinolato rings (quinolinol-N, Cg(4) and quinolinol-O, Cg(5)) enhances the stability of 2D plane (Cg(3)---Cg(4), 3.475(6); symmetry, 3-x, -y, 2-z; Cg(4)---Cg(4), 3.114(3); symmetry, x, -1+y, z).

Photoluminescence properties:

The photoluminescence properties of HL is taken in MeOH and its complexes were studied at room temperature (298 K) (Table 2, Fig. 4) in DMF solution. Emission of HL is observed at 346 nm and quantum yield, ϕ_{HL} is 0.17. Life time

Fig. 3. Hydrogen bonded chain propagation and formation of 2D plane.

Fig. 4. Emission spectra of HL; $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{L})_2]$ (1); $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2); $[\text{NiL}_2]$ (3); $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (4); $[\text{ZnL}_2]$ (5).

at excited state of the ligand is 3.09 ns (Fig. 5; χ_2 , 1.08; k_r , 5.554×10^7 ; k_{nr} , 26.90×10^7). The transition metal complexes show weak fluorescence except $[\text{ZnL}_2]$ (d^{10}) in DMF solvent (Table 2), which suggests paramagnetic quenching of magnetically active metal complexes²⁹. Intense emission at 414 nm of $[\text{ZnL}_2]$ is assigned to the (π - π^*) intraligand fluorescence and are red shifted by 68 nm compared to HL.

Cyclic voltammetry:

Redox properties of the complexes have been studied by cyclic voltammetry (CV) using a platinum working elec-

Fig. 5. Exponential decay profile (●) and fitting curve (—) of HL in methanol. Excitation is carried out at 243 nm.

trode. The complexes show quasireversible reductive response at -0.4 to -0.5 V alongwith an irreversible peak at -0.8 V. These are referring to azo/azo⁻ and azo⁻/azo⁼. This is supported from free ligand data which have shown reduction responses at more negative potential -0.75 V (peak-to-peak separation, 160 mV) and -1.05 V. The coordination of HL brings down LUMO to lower energy and shows lower redox potential than free ligand data. A representative voltammogram is shown in Fig. 6. The oxidative response is only observed for $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2) which corresponds to $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ couple at 0.65 V (180 mV). The cyclic voltammogram of

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of (a) $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (1), (b) $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2) and (c) $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (3) in MeCN solution using Pt-disk working electrode, Ag/AgCl reference electrode, $[\text{NBu}_4][\text{ClO}_4]$ supporting electrolyte at 50 mV s^{-1} scan rate.

copper(II) complexes, **3**, show reductive response at ~ -0.4 V versus Ag/AgCl, Cl^- which may be referred to $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ response. The voltammogram also shows a sharp anodic part at ~ -0.2 V, possibly due to the $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}}/\text{Cu}^0$ couple⁴³. The reduced Cu^0 is absorbed on the electrode surface as evidenced from the narrow width of the anodic response with a large peak current. On carrying out the experiment with back scan going to negative potential to -0.6 V does not observe such large anodic current at -0.2 V. Other complexes $[\text{NiL}_2]$ (**3**) and $[\text{ZnL}_2]$ (**5**) do not show metal oxidation response while azo reductions are observed at -0.5 (quasireversible) and -1.00 V (irreversible).

Magnetic data and EPR spectra:

The magnetic moment are recorded at 300 K and μ_{eff} are 4.88 BM ($[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, **1**), 1.8 BM ($[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, **2**), 0.14 BM ($[\text{NiL}_2]$, **3**), 1.54 BM ($[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, **4**). These data support d^5 (**1**), low-spin d^7 (**2**), square planer diamagnetic d^8 (**3**) and d^9 (**4**) electronic configuration of the complexes. The EPR spectra at solid state show existence of active paramagnetic electron to Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes (Fig. 7). The EPR spectrum of **1** ($[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$) in MeCN at 77 K display $g \approx 2$, $m_s = +1/2$ to $-1/2$ fine structure transition splits into six hyperfine lines as expected for $^{55}\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}$ complex ($I = 5/2$) along with superfine splitting (Fig. 8). A notable feature of

Fig. 7. Solid state EPR spectra of (a) $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (**1**), (b) $[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (**2**), (c) $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ at 300 K (**3**), (d) $[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (**3**) at 77 K in MeCN glass.

Fig. 8. EPR spectrum of $[\text{Mn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{L})_2]$ (1) in MeCN solution at 77 K.

the spectra is the relatively low value of the hyperfine coupling constant A , 80-90 G. Each hyperfine shows doublet splitting at 77 K which suggests interaction of donor centre N of the with Mn^{II} .

Solid state EPR spectra of **4** ($[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$) at room temperature (298 K) are weakly resolved. The resolution is better at 77 K in MeCN solution. The complexes show usual four line (^{63}Cu , $I = 3/2$) EPR spectra and are anisotropic at higher magnetic field. They exhibit axial spectra with g_{\parallel} 2.12 and A_{\parallel} having a range from $148 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The results are in general agreement with the electronic spectra, which also suggest the existence of distorted square pyramidal. From the observed g -tensor values of the Cu^{II} complexes it is clear that $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ agrees with the ground state configuration of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ giving $^2B_{1g}$ as the ground state.

Conclusion

5-(Pyridin-3-ylidiazanyl)quinolin-8-ol (HL) is a bidentate N, O anionic chelator and forms complexes $[\text{ML}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ ($M = \text{Mn}, \text{Co}, \text{Cu}$) and $\text{M}'\text{L}_2$ ($\text{M}' = \text{Ni}$ and Zn). The structure of $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ has been confirmed by X-ray crystallography as octahedral. Magnetic and redox properties of the complexes are described.

Supplementary materials

Crystallographic data for the structures have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC No. 1018809 of $[\text{MnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>).

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